

STRENGTHENING MONUMENTS WITH TRC

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ABSTRACT

The use of textile reinforced concrete (TRC) as a strengthening measure is a simple way of maintaining existing concrete structures and ensuring their long-term load-bearing capacity and serviceability. This method offers clear economic and technical advantages over conventional methods such as shotcrete, particularly for heritage structures. The thin strengthening layers are barely visible and preserve the original visual appearance, while introducing only a small amount of additional weight and moisture. A large number of listed buildings, complex shell structures and even bridges, have been repaired or strengthened using this construction method. The most important of these practical applications are presented here.

KEYWORDS

Strengthening; textile reinforced concrete; carbon reinforced concrete; listed buildings

INTRODUCTION

Since its development, reinforced concrete has established itself as the world's most important building material. However, in addition to its many advantages, such as strength, ductility and economy, reinforced concrete also has some significant disadvantages. In particular, the lack of durability due to corrosion problems of the steel reinforcement can be detrimental. In addition, the high consumption of concrete leads to a global shortage of natural resources such as water, sand and rock, and the energy-intensive production of cement causes huge amounts of CO₂ emissions.

Many buildings and bridges in Germany were constructed after the end of the Second World War and have reached their original lifespan of over 60 years. As a result of material damage, changes in use and increased loads during this time, many structures no longer have sufficient load-bearing capacity. To avoid demolition and replacement, the structures can be repaired or strengthened using a variety of systems.

The most common reinforcement methods are shotcrete or CFRP lamellae. In recent years, another option has emerged in the form of Textile Reinforced Concrete (TRC), which consists of a thin, high-performance layer of fine grained concrete with textile reinforcement. Such layers are typically 10 to 20 mm thick, depending on the application. The textile reinforcement consists of continuous technical fibres, which are combined into yarns by impregnation. The yarns are then further processed into grids. Fibre materials that can be used include alkali resistant glass (AR glass), basalt and, most importantly, carbon. General information on carbon concrete as a building material and its applications can be found in (Curbach et al., 2023; Lorenz et al., 2015; Müller et al., 2020; Scheerer et al., 2019). It has been successfully researched and economically applied in numerous practical projects over the last decades on the basis of the general technical approval Z-31.10-182 (DIBt, 2021) introduced in Germany, as presented in (Sandmann et al., 2023).

Strengthening with TRC is naturally concerned with older reinforced concrete structures that need to be made fit for further use. This saves time, costs, materials and resources in all areas, including the CO₂ balance. Strengthening with TRC also takes account of historic preservation concerns. The intervention in the building fabric is minimal, the thin layers used do not carry too much moisture into the structure and are visually unobtrusive. The appearance and proportions of structures and components are maintained. Relatively little old fabric needs to be removed - in fact only the mostly damaged concrete cover - which best supports the conservation task.

PROCESS STEPS FOR STRENGTHENING WITH TRC

The steps required to strengthen reinforced and prestressed concrete members with TRC are similar in many respects to the usual procedures mentioned above and are divided into substrate preparation, application and curing. The first step is to prepare the surface of the old concrete member according to the specifications in (DIBt, 2021). Loose material and contaminants must be removed and defects, cracks or spalling must be professionally repaired to stop or prevent corrosion of the existing reinforcement. The surface should then be roughened to the designer's specification. Suitable methods include high pressure water blasting or sand blasting. The depth of roughness required to ensure the bond between the old concrete and the strengthening layer, usually 1.0 to 1.5 mm, is used as a quality criterion (Curbach et al., 2022). As a further test, the adhesive strength of the existing structure is randomly checked. The expected value of the characteristic value of the adhesive strength must be at least 1.0 MPa. The substrate must be pre-wetted and re-wetted at 2-hour intervals during the day prior to the actual application of the strengthening measure.

The strengthening measure is applied in layers by spraying or manual application as shown in Figure 1. The textile grid is worked into the first layer of fresh concrete using light pressure. Subsequent layers are applied to the underlying fresh concrete layer at a spacing of approximately 3 to 5 mm, depending on the type of grid used. This process is repeated until the number of layers required by the static calculations has been achieved. The surface of the top layer is produced according to the design specifications. Careful curing by constant watering and covering with a damp sheet is essential to avoid shrinkage cracks in the thin reinforcement.

Figure 1: Strengthening process of existing structures with TRC (Photo: TU Dresden)

PRACTICAL APPLICATIONS

Since the first projects strengthened with textile concrete, such as the hypar shell in Schweinfurt in 2006 or the barrel roof in Zwickau in 2008 (Erhard et al., 2015), the applicability has expanded to a wide variety of load-bearing structures. The constructions to be strengthened can be general buildings, bridges, halls, silos, and much more. In recent years, significant projects have been carried out, mainly with carbon concrete, which reflect this diversity in a representative way. Some of the most important projects are described in more detail below.

Repair of the Hypar Shell in Magdeburg

Hypar shells are multiple curved structures in the shape of a hyperbolic paraboloid. One of the largest reinforced concrete shells of this type in Germany was built in Magdeburg in 1969. Designed by the German civil engineer Ulrich Müther, it was used for many years as a multi-purpose hall for trade fairs, concerts and similar events (Riegelmann et al., 2021). It has been a listed building since 1990.

The roof structure consists of four assembled hyperbolic paraboloids made of reinforced concrete, which together span a base area of 48 m x 48 m without supports and are each only 7 cm thick (Hentschel et al., 2019), see Figure 2. In the center of the structure, additional light bands are arranged to connect the shells and emphasize the slender appearance. The edges of the shell segments are braced with beams, which transfer the vertical loads to the foundations via steel columns. The majority of the loads are transferred through inclined reinforced concrete columns connected at the lowest points of the shell segments and connected under the structure by prestressed concrete tendons.

Figure 2: Strengthening process of the hyper shell in Magdeburg with carbon reinforced concrete (Photo: M. Bredt)

As a result of construction defects during erection and weathering during use, there was extensive damage to the structure, particularly to the structural waterproofing, columns and thin shell construction. This was evidenced by exposed and severely corroded reinforcement, moisture ingress, extensive concrete spalling and gravel pockets. As a result, the structure had to be closed in 1997. Demolition of the structure could be avoided, but conventional repair methods such as shotcrete reinforcement were out of the question, mainly due to the high dead weight involved. In addition to the damage, a survey revealed that the planned formwork thickness of 7 cm was undercut by 1 to 2 cm in many areas and that the reinforcement had smaller bar diameters than planned. As a solution to save the structure, it was decided in 2017 to strengthen it with carbon concrete (Schumann et al., 2021). In addition to repairing the damage to ensure sufficient stability and durability, the aim was to achieve the required 7 cm layer thickness over the entire area and to increase the bending and normal force capacity by up to 50% compared to the existing load-bearing condition. Based on a feasibility study, a 1 cm thick strengthening layer of fine concrete with a maximum grain size of 1 mm and a biaxial carbon grid was applied to the top and bottom of the shell. The design tensile strength of the reinforcement is 1100 MPa with a reinforcement cross-section of 70.5 mm²/m. The rehabilitation works started in February 2020 and were completed in July 2022.

Renovation of the Beyer-Bau of the Dresden University of Technology

The Beyer Building is a university building designed by the German architect Martin Dülfer and inaugurated in 1913. It is located in the center of the campus and traditionally houses the civil engineers. The five-story building, with its distinctive Lohrmann Observatory tower shown in Figure 3, is one of the University's landmarks. The main structure, including floor slabs and roof trusses, was one of the first buildings in Dresden to be constructed in steel reinforced concrete.

The floor slabs are designed as a slab-beam structure with beam spans of up to 11 m at intervals of 2 to 3 m. Based on component tests, the concrete of the beams is classified in the non-standard strength class C8/10 (characteristic cylinder compressive strength 8 MPa, characteristic cube compressive strength 10 MPa), that of the floor slabs in class C20/25. The thickness of the floor slabs is often only 8 cm. The longitudinal bending reinforcement in the beams is made of plain steel rebars with a diameter of 30 mm and a characteristic tensile strength of 260 MPa. The static recalculation revealed significant structural deficiencies for these components. Here, too, the structure was maintained by applying carbon concrete in the bending tension zone (Curbach et al., 2022).

Figure 3: Beyer-Bau at the Dresden University of Technologies (Photo: Stefan Gröschel)

The slabs and beams were strengthened with unidirectional reinforcement in accordance with the general technical approval (DIBt, 2021). For the slabs, a 10 mm layer of carbon concrete proved sufficient due to the design flexural load capacity. For the beams, 1 or 2 strengthening layers with a total thickness of 10 to 15 mm were applied to the underside of the web, depending on the static requirements, with the warp direction of the reinforcement being aligned with the load-transmitting direction of the member. Due to the low strength of the existing concrete and the associated low surface tensile strength, a safe transfer of forces between the strengthening layer and the existing concrete could no longer be guaranteed with more than two layers. Instead, the carbon reinforcement was extended into the tensile zone on the web sides where necessary. Due to the boundary conditions for the strengthening of the beams described above, this measure did not comply with the provisions of the approval, so that approval had to be obtained on a case-by-case basis. As part of this approval, a significant increase in load-bearing capacity was demonstrated by means of large-scale component tests that reflected the real conditions in the existing structure. The strengthening work started in September 2021 and was completed in 2022.

Strengthening of the First Motorway Bridge in Germany

The A 648 motorway crosses the River Nidda near the city of Frankfurt in Germany with three prestressed concrete bridges. The bridges have a length of approximately 70 m over three spans and consist of double chord T-beams. Details of the structures can be found in (Steinbock, Pelke, & Ost, 2021). Two of the three substructures date from the 1960s and 1970s respectively and have already been strengthened with carbon concrete. In the case of substructure 3, which was completed in 1971 and shown in Figure 4, this was done in 2021.

Figure 4: Side view of the bridge 3 over the river Nidda (Photo: Oliver Steinbock)

The bridges are reinforced with so-called sigma-oval prestressing steels, which are susceptible to stress corrosion cracking (Steinbock & Wetzel, 2021). The presence of stress corrosion cracking could not be completely ruled out even by tendon soundings, and a recalculation did not provide sufficient indication of failure due to deformation and cracking, so the remaining service life of substructure 3 was limited to the end of 2020. Due to these boundary conditions and the infrastructural importance of the bridge, the selected strengthening measure had to meet the requirements of sufficient post-repair signal behaviour, rapid feasibility - also due to the limited remaining service life - and a minimally invasive intervention in the existing structure gauge.

The comparison of different strengthening methods in (Steinbock, Bösche, & Schumann, 2021) showed that carbon concrete is the preferred option. As in the Beyer-Bau, the material combination consists of uniaxial carbon layers and a fine concrete. Reinforcement was reduced to the amount actually required and staggered accordingly. As a result, bottom reinforcement was only provided in the approximately 17.5 m long edge spans. Three continuous outer layers of reinforcement and two additional layers in areas directly on the old concrete section were installed per chord (Steinbock, Teworte, & Neis, 2021). For structural reasons, up to six layers of carbon grid were required on the top of the bridge, installed in five strips on the up to 12 m wide deck. Four layers are placed only in the support area, while the outer two layers are placed along the entire length of the bridge to be part of the roadway structure at the same time with the inert and crack dispersing properties of the carbon reinforcement. The staggered reinforcement must always be placed on the inside of the old concrete section to prevent delamination. The arrangement of the reinforcement is shown in Figure 5.

The theoretical preliminary considerations for the strengthening measures were successfully verified by static and cyclic component tests prior to implementation. It was shown that the maximum load-bearing capacity could be achieved without premature delamination of the six layers of reinforcement. Of particular importance is the precise alignment of the reinforcement layers or wires using alignment aids to ensure the effectiveness of the high level of reinforcement and the transfer of transverse tensile forces to the old concrete section. Cyclic loading also showed no negative effect on the structural performance.

Figure 5: Staggered arrangement of the carbon reinforcement (Graphics: Oliver Steinbock)

Restoration of the historic Naila arch bridge

The Naila concrete arch bridge was built in 1910 as part of a railway line and was used as such until 1973. After 1973, the bridge was decommissioned and the tracks removed, so no further use or maintenance took place. In 2016, the listed structure was renovated and repaired with carbon concrete as part of a planned conversion to a pedestrian and cycle bridge (Al-Jamous, 2017).

The bridge consists of four unreinforced main arches of up to 1.4 m thick stamped concrete, see Figure 6. Due to the concrete technology of the time and the manual layer-by-layer construction, the concrete structure of the bridge was severely disturbed and the strength was highly variable. There were voids, flaws and cracks due to various causes such as loading, concrete joints and settlement. As a result of moisture ingress into the structure, water-bearing separation cracks with associated lime sinter plumes were also found. Overall, however, the stability of the structure was not compromised from a structural point of view. The aim of the planned repair was to restore the original geometry and appearance, not least for heritage reasons. To this end, the arches and facing masonry were repaired and the cornice was renewed. A top coat of concrete with waterproofing and surfacing was applied to the upper side. The carbon concrete work concentrated on crack-bridging repairs to the undersides of the four arches.

Figure 6: Completed bridge renovation Naila arch bridge (Photo: Institute of Concrete Structures, TU Dresden)

The choice of material was carbon concrete for economic reasons. Typical repair methods such as crack injection, concrete replacement and surface protection systems had to be ruled out. With crack injection, there was a risk of uncontrolled migration of grout into the voids of the arch fill. Crack-bridging coatings, on the other hand, prevent the diffusion of water vapour from the interior of the structure. A reinforced shotcrete repair was also out of the question because it would have required the removal of a 10cm layer of old concrete before applying three layers of shotcrete of different strengths to match the modulus of the existing concrete, to ensure sufficient concrete cover of the steel reinforcement and therefore durability, and to restore the visual appearance. The carbon concrete repair only required 2 to 4 cm of old concrete to be removed. The substrate was then re-profiled with a low strength spray mortar to achieve the required minimum characteristic surface tensile strength of 1.0 N/mm² (DIBt, 2021). Two layers of carbon grid were then embedded in a sprayed fine concrete with a maximum grain size of 1 mm and a total thickness of 2 cm. The work was carried out exclusively by a certified company with trained personnel in accordance with the general technical approval (DIBt, 2021). This resulted in a cost saving of 20% was achieved compared to the other options mentioned (Al-Jamous, 2017).

Strengthening of a Pedestrian Bridge in Germany

The Naumburg Pedestrian Bridge was built of reinforced concrete in 1893/94, making it a nationally significant pioneering example of early reinforced concrete construction in Germany, according to the State Office for the Preservation of Monuments and Archaeology. It is now a listed building.

The supporting structure of the bridge is a flat concrete arch with steel reinforcement to absorb bending moments, as can be seen in Figure 7. This arch is supported on both sides by stamped concrete abutments. As a result of exposure to the elements, the steel reinforcement has become severely corroded and has been repaired several times. However, further repairs and bending reinforcement were required to maintain the structure (Schumann et al., 2022). The flexural tension zone needed to be strengthened and the statically required bending reinforcement in the arch needed to be supplemented. A shotcrete reinforcement would have had a lasting negative impact on the appearance of the bridge and was therefore rejected for heritage reasons. A thin layer of carbon concrete, on the other hand, does not detract from the bridge's appearance, as the few millimeters of reinforcement required almost disappear into the layer of concrete to be re-profiled. This makes it possible to offer a refurbishment option suitable for listed buildings.

Figure 7: Side view of the Naumburg Pedestrian Bridge after restoration (Photo: CARBOCON GMBH)

The strengthening work began in July 2021. On the underside of the bridge, two layers of textile carbon reinforcement were installed along the load direction of the bridge. The strengthening layer ends at the abutment point, before the bridge arch is integrated. At this point, the existing reinforcement was in a non-critical condition. In addition to the flexural reinforcement, the bridge was rehabilitated with one surrounding layer of textile concrete to prevent moisture ingress. The warp yarns of the carbon fabric are laid in the transverse direction of the bridge. At the same time, the mineral material does not hinder water vapor diffusion, allowing moisture to escape from the interior of the structure. The measure was successfully completed in September 2021.

Rehabilitation of the Bretzig Road Bridge

Another example for the use of textile concrete as a rehabilitation measure of small road bridges is illustrated by the fictional example of the Bretzig Bridge (not carried out). Apart from the static strengthening, the idea of providing a protective layer around the body of the bridge to extend its service life was also of interest. Many structures of this type have the problem of insufficient concrete cover, which can be permanently restored or increased with textile concrete.

Figure 8: Damage to the Bretinig Bridge prior to its renovation (Photos: Harald Michler)

The Bretinig Bridge is a typical example of a road bridge carrying a national road over a small stream. These are usually reinforced concrete slab bridges with no structural deficiencies. They are robust structures with spans of 5 to 7 m and widths of 12 to 14 m, but maintenance has often been neglected. The resulting damage patterns are shown in Figure 8. Concrete spalling due to reinforcement corrosion is often observed locally. Causes include errors during construction and mechanical damage during service life. If the bridge waterproofing is intact, it is sufficient to repair only the damaged areas with a concrete repair. The easy-to-apply, thin textile concrete layer of carbon grid with shotcrete and very good crack-bridging effect finally ensures durability for many years.

CONCLUSIONS

The sustainable, resource-efficient and CO₂-saving maintenance of existing buildings is becoming increasingly important in the construction industry. TRC - especially carbon fiber reinforced concrete - has proven a high technical and economic potential in practice compared to conventional methods. This is due to its high tensile strength, corrosion resistance and very thin reinforcement layers with low dead weight and low additional moisture. Clear room heights or clearances are only slightly restricted. This allows for efficient and cost-effective strengthening. As a result, many buildings, shell structures and load-bearing components can be saved from demolition and replacement, and their service life can be significantly extended. This is particularly true of historic buildings. Textile reinforced concrete is not only used for conventional buildings, but also for the strengthening of complex and filigree listed structures where there is little impact on the appearance. This is how the Beyer-Bau and the Hyparschale in Magdeburg were saved. It has also made the leap into bridge construction, where many structures, especially in Germany, are in urgent need of repair and could be preserved for the future with this building material. The two bridges in Naila and Naumburg demonstrate the successful and impressive use of TRC, which is almost invisible to the naked eye.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

No data was assembled for the production of this paper.